

1 **Head and neck cancer by HPV type.**

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7 A major purpose of this study was to identify by RNA-sequencing aspects of a specific gene signature for
8 head and neck cancers resulting from HPV35 infection by comparison to those caused by infection by
9 HPV16 or HPV18. We demonstrate here specific activation of homeoboxes *Pax3* and *Sry* in HPV35+ head
10 and neck cancer. Instead, activation of *Foxj1* was a specific feature of HPV16+ head and neck cancer. In
11 cancer caused by both HPV16 and by HPV35, tumors activated expression of *Tcam1p* and *Zyg11a*, as
12 well as homeoboxes *Tlx2* and *Lhx2*, while silencing immunologic effectors *Cxcl14* and *Il20*.

13 Citations

14 1. Agalliu, I., Gapstur, S., Chen, Z., Wang, T., Anderson, R.L., Teras, L., Kreimer, A.R., Hayes, R.B.,
15 Freedman, N.D. and Burk, R.D., 2016. Associations of oral α -, β -, and γ -human papillomavirus types with
16 risk of incident head and neck cancer. *JAMA oncology*, 2(5), pp.599-606.

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